

Al-Ghazali Model Helps in Managing Anxiety on the Academic Performance : A Case Study

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Students; anxiety; academic performance; family socioeconomic status	Anxiety is a common feeling experienced by every human being. It causes individuals to live in constant fear, tension, and stress. A certain level of anxiety is necessary within a person, as it can enhance motivation and life performance while also helping to manage ongoing problems. One example of anxiety faced by secondary school students is when they receive their examination results. This is because they worry that their results may not be as promising as expected. At this adolescent stage, they are easily disturbed by feelings of worry, restlessness, and stress, especially when they fail to resolve problems rationally. It is even more distressing when their anxiety stems from environmental factors such as a low-income family background. Therefore, the purpose of this case study, conducted on a 15-year-old subject, is to identify the causes of their anxiety regarding academic performance. Additionally, this study aims to test the effectiveness of the Al-Ghazali model in managing the subject's anxiety. This qualitative study employs observation, interviews, and document analysis methods. Through the application of the Al-Ghazali model, the subject was observed to be more motivated to strive for better results in future examinations. It is hoped that the findings of this study can serve as a guide for relevant parties in managing students' academic anxiety more efficiently, benefiting the general public and, more specifically, secondary school students in the country.

Article history:

Type :	Received in revised form	Accepted	Available online
Research Article	14 th July 2025	14 th July 2025	30 th July 2025

1. Introduction

In today's world, mental health issues have become an increasingly significant concern, particularly following the COVID-19 pandemic. This is evident from the rising statistics of the Mental Health and Psychosocial Support Services (MHPSS) helpline, which recorded 44,061 calls in 2020, increasing significantly to 212,319 calls in 2022 [16].

The World Health Organization (WHO) (2022) defines mental health as a state of physical, mental, social, and spiritual well-being. These four aspects must be fulfilled for an individual to achieve an optimal level of health [18][19].

Furthermore, in 2019, the Malaysian Ministry of Health recorded that 2.3% of adults and 9.5% of children aged 10-15 years experienced mental health issues. The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) also reported that 12.3% of adolescents aged 10-17 years residing in the People's Housing Project (PPR) in the Klang Valley suffered from mental health problems [16]. One of the most prevalent mental health issues is anxiety.

Anxiety is a common experience for every individual. However, if not managed effectively, it can be detrimental to a person's well-being. According to Kamus Dewan (Fourth Edition), anxiety refers to feelings of worry, concern, or distress. Anxiety often stems from stress, and both conditions share similar symptoms, making them difficult to distinguish [10].

There are various factors contributing to anxiety, such as age, gender, and financial status. According to Baloran et al. (2020), financial difficulties and academic performance are among the primary causes of anxiety [3].

Numerous other factors can contribute to anxiety among students. These include financial struggles, academic performance pressure, competition with peers, persistent pressure to succeed, and concerns about the future. Such stressors can significantly impact students' academic performance [10].

One of the key aspects emphasized in the Malaysian Education Development Plan (PPPM) (2013-2025) is student well-being. A student's excellence is not solely measured by academic achievements but also by the effectiveness of the schooling process in a holistic manner. Additionally, a student is considered to have attained well-being if they can achieve personal fulfillment.

According to Rahayu et al. (2020), various constraints from different aspects of life can lead students to experience stress, lose focus, and become demotivated in their learning journey [12]. This can negatively affect their academic performance.

In conclusion, a student's academic success should not be measured solely by the number of A's they achieve but should also be evaluated based on their character and moral development.

1.1 Background of the Study

The definition of anxiety, according to al-Ghazali, as cited by Salasiah Hanin (2016) in her book *Kaedah Penyelesaian Masalah Spiritual Dalam Kaunseling Menurut al-Ghazali*, refers to a feeling closely associated with fear (al-Khauf) [14]. Al-Ghazali further elaborates on the causes of anxiety or fear among individuals, such as the fear of Allah's punishment and the fear of death.

In his book, al-Ghazali also explains that moderate levels of anxiety can be beneficial, as they serve as motivation for self-improvement. For example, a student who feels anxious about not performing well in an exam will strive to study harder to succeed. However, in the absence of anxiety, the student may lack determination and adopt a complacent attitude. On the other hand, excessive anxiety can be detrimental, as it may lead to depression, sadness, and a pessimistic outlook on one's abilities.

Al-Ghazali also provides solutions for managing anxiety, emphasizing that the treatment should be based on its underlying causes. If anxiety stems from the loss of wealth or status, the remedy is to overcome materialistic attachments and excessive love for worldly possessions.

According to al-Ghazali, individuals experiencing extreme anxiety should continue striving for a better life while maintaining faith in the sustenance provided by Allah. This aligns with the Islamic teaching that discourages despair, as stated in the Quran (Surah al-Zumar, verse 53) [13]. In conclusion, Muslims are encouraged to avoid hopelessness, continuously strive for self-improvement, and place their trust in Allah in all aspects of life.

1.2 Research Issue

The subject of this study is the eldest of six siblings. The subject's parents face financial difficulties, with the family classified as low-income. The subject's mother operates a small business daily from morning until evening, while the father has recently secured a new job as a supplier of laundry detergent.

As the eldest child, the subject is compelled to make sacrifices, often missing school to assist the mother in preparing goods for sale in the early morning. Typically, the subject only attends school two to three days a week, with the remaining days dedicated to helping the mother with her business. Due to frequent absences, the subject has received a second warning letter from the school administration.

Despite these challenges, the subject is determined to improve academic performance in the new academic year. However, the subject also experiences anxiety about achieving this goal. Additionally, the subject remains committed to assisting the mother without expecting any financial reward, considering it a responsibility as the eldest child in the family.

1.3 Problem Statement

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adolescents are defined as individuals aged between 10 and 19, while youth are those aged between 15 and 24. Adolescence is a transitional phase between childhood and adulthood, occurring between the ages of 10 and 19 [18]. This stage is crucial in human development, laying the foundation for overall well-being and good health.

During adolescence, significant changes occur in physical, cognitive, and psychosocial development. This phase influences how individuals perceive and respond to challenges, how they think, and how they make decisions. Adawiyah (2020) states that adolescence is a stage where emotional and mental maturity begins to develop, allowing individuals to learn and adapt to new experiences [1].

The rising trend of mental health issues among adolescents is a growing concern. According to the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF), approximately 86 million adolescents aged 15 to 19 years have been identified as experiencing mental health problems [5].

Kipli, Maisarah, Saemah Rahman, and Shahlan Surat explain that anxiety is an emotion often accompanied by tension, which can cause physiological responses such as increased blood pressure. If anxiety is not managed well, it can lead to feelings of sadness, depression, pessimism, and negative self-perception [6].

Norlela Ahmad et al. (2021) emphasize that a family's socioeconomic status significantly influences a child's life from birth. Every individual is born into different family backgrounds and circumstances. Environmental factors such as living conditions, family income level, and parental education play a crucial role in shaping a person's development. Subra (2019) highlights that a low socioeconomic status can be a barrier to success due to a lack of resources, facilities, and a comfortable living environment provided by parents [9].

Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory states that fundamental needs must be met before progressing to higher levels of personal development. The first level of the hierarchy consists of physiological needs, which must be fulfilled before an individual can focus on other aspects of

growth. If these needs are adequately met, students are more likely to be motivated and thrive in a conducive learning environment [11].

Figure 1. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

1.4 Objectives

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To identify the causes of the subject's anxiety towards academic performance.
2. To assess the effectiveness of Al-Ghazali's model in managing the subject's anxiety.

1.5 Research Questions

The research questions are as follows:

1. What are the causes of the subject's anxiety towards academic performance?
2. Is Al-Ghazali's model effective in helping to manage the subject's anxiety?

2. Methodology

The researcher of this study employed a qualitative research approach using observation, interviews, and document analysis to collect data. The data gathered was triangulated through source triangulation and analyzed using thematic analysis and content analysis techniques. Thematic analysis was chosen to obtain data and measure the validity of the collected data. The study was conducted over four weeks.

2.1 Research Design

This study follows a non-experimental research design, specifically a case study approach. Case studies are a qualitative research approach that allows for an in-depth examination of the subject's experiences. This method was chosen to gather detailed data through careful observation, ensuring alignment with the research objectives and addressing the research questions effectively.

2.2 Sampling

To ensure meaningful data collection and achieve the study's objectives, the researcher chose to use a sampling method to select the research subjects after consultation with a counselor. Two criteria were established to identify the research subject:

1. The subject has a history of absenteeism from school, having received a first or second warning letter from the school.
2. The subject experiences varying levels of anxiety (mild/moderate/severe) based on the DASS Mental Health Screening Test.

2.3 Instruments, Validity, and Reliability

The researcher ensured the validity and reliability of the data using the source triangulation method. Source triangulation involves gathering information from different sources. The researcher conducted interviews with three sources: the counselor, the class teacher, and the subject's subject teacher. These interviews confirmed that the subject's absenteeism was accurate. Additionally, the researcher used methodological triangulation to verify the validity of the data through observations, interviews, and document analysis.

Instruments used in this study include the DASS (Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale) test, conducted in collaboration with the counselor. The results of the DASS test were discussed with the counselor. This instrument was used because the subject had expressed concern about their academic performance during the interview.

According to Maisarah Kipli, Saemah Rahman, and Shahlan Surat (2022), the DASS test contains 21 items [10], used to identify a person's mental health status, including levels of depression, anxiety, and stress.

2.4 Data Collection and Analysis Methods

Data collection in this study was carried out through semi-structured interviews to gather information about the subjects' anxiety regarding their academic performance. During the interview sessions, the researcher recorded the conversations to ensure accurate, clear, and repeatable data for future reference.

To address the second research question regarding the effectiveness of al-Ghazali's model, the researcher conducted both structured and unstructured interviews with the subject. The effectiveness of al-Ghazali's model was assessed through its application during the intervention sessions.

3. Findings and Discussion

In this section, the data analysis is focused on two research questions which are identifying the causes of the subject's anxiety regarding their academic performance and testing the effectiveness of the al-Ghazali model in helping reduce anxiety about academic performance. However, before analyzing the data from these two research questions, the researcher will first analyze the findings from the sampling through:

3.1.1 Source Triangulation: Interviews with 3 Sources; Counselor, Class Teacher, and Subject Teacher

Table 1

Thematic Analysis of Interviews Between 3 Sources Regarding the Subject's Absence from School

Source	Response
S1: Counselor	"...the subject of this study has an issue with absenteeism from school".
S2: Class Teacher	"...the subject of this study has received a second warning letter due to frequent school absenteeism".
S3: Subject Teacher	"...the subject of this study frequently misses school, and there are days when they are absent from school".

3.1.2 Method Triangulation: Through Attendance Records in (RPH), Classmate Interviews, and Supporting Document Findings of the Warning Letter Regarding the Subject's Absence from School

Table 2
Thematic Analysis of Classmate Interviews Regarding the Subject's Absence from School

Source	Response
Classmate	"... the subject of the study frequently misses school to help their mother with her business."

3.1.3 Analysis of the DASS Test Results Conducted on the Research Subject

Table 3
Analysis of the Mental Health Screening Test (DASS) Results of the Research Subject

	Score	Level
Depression	6.00	Mild
Anxiety	1.00	Normal
Stress	1.00	Normal

Table 3 above shows the results of the DASS test conducted on the research subject. The subject's anxiety level scored 6.00, indicating a mild level of anxiety. Meanwhile, the depression and stress levels both scored 1.00, which is within the normal range. This indicates that the research subject is experiencing mild anxiety, which needs to be managed to prevent it from escalating to a more severe level.

4. Analysis of Data Findings for the Research Questions

4.1 First Research Question: Causes of Anxiety Regarding Academic Performance

Table 4. Thematic Analysis of the Interview with the Subject Regarding the Causes of Anxiety Towards Academic Performance. Researcher's Question: "What are the causes of your anxiety regarding academic performance?"

No.	Response from the subject of the study.	Minute	Theme
1	"In the morning, my mom will cook a lot of dishes to sell. Every day she will be selling from morning until evening. As for my dad, recently he got a new job as a laundry detergent delivery man to stores."	3:27	Low-income family living standard
2	"...you are the hope of your mother and father, you have to help our family no matter how difficult our situation is."	5:00	The eldest child and considered as the family's hope
3	"During the mid-year exams, there were a few subjects I didn't take because I helped my mother with her business."	11:00	Weak in some subjects
4	"...i know I'm weak in academics, but I am determined to make my mother happy and help ease my family's situation. But hmm... I don't know what to do to help myself."	20:01	Lack of confidence in self-potential

Table 5

Analysis of the Mid-Year Exam Results (2023) for the Study Subject by Subject
(Source: Mid-Year Exam, 2023)

Subjects	Score (%)	Level of Mastery
Malay	36	3
English	26	-
Mathematics	13	1
History	0	1
Geography	11	1
ASK	-	-
RBT	-	-
PI	-	-
PSV	50	4

The findings of the analysis of the mid-year exam results (2023) show that three (3) subjects were not taken by the study subject due to their absence from school. In addition, five (5) subjects failed, and only two (2) subjects passed. This table proves that the study subject was also absent during the exams, as they were helping their mother with her business.

After examining the issues faced by the study subject, the researcher proposed an intervention that could be applied to help the subject manage their anxiety regarding academic performance. This intervention was carried out over eight (8) days. The effectiveness of this intervention, using the al-Ghazali module, was demonstrated through observation and interviews.

The researcher observed more positive behavior from the study subject, including discussing lessons with their classmates. This indicates that the subject started to adopt a more proactive approach to their studies. Furthermore, the researcher conducted an unstructured interview with the study subject.

Table 6

Thematic Analysis of the Interview on the Effectiveness of the 'My Daily Study Planner' Intervention, Adapted from the Quranic Soul Intervention by Ismail, M. B. (2016)

No.	The response of the research subject
1.	<i>"I feel more organized when I make this schedule. I've never made a study schedule like this before. This schedule helps me to study with my friends and do a bit more revision than I did before the previous exam."</i>

4.2 Effectiveness of the Al-Ghazali Model in Managing Academic Anxiety of the Study Subject

4.2.1 Intervention 'My Daily Study Planner' Adapted from the Quranic Soul Intervention by Ismail, M. B. (2016)

The Quranic Soul intervention proposed by the researcher contains spiritual elements that form the foundation of an individual's behavior and character. Al-Ghazali (1998) explained that within the soul of a teenager, there are elements such as the heart, spirit (ruh), desires (nafsu), and intellect (akal) that influence their thoughts and actions. These components are crucial in shaping a person's mental and emotional state, which in turn impacts their academic performance and overall well-being [13].

4.2.2 Al-Ghazali's Model in the Approach of Spiritual Counseling

The spiritual counseling approach is an approach that combines religious elements sourced from the Quran and Hadith (Nor Ezdianie & Mohd Tajudin, 2019). According to Salasiah Hanin (2010), Al-Ghazali divides spiritual guidance into two words, namely guidance (Al-irshad) and spiritual (Al-nafsiy) [14]. Both of these methods are summarized as a way of guiding and showing the path toward goodness based on Sharia.

4.2.3 Tazkiyah Al-Nafs and Mujahadah Al-Nafs Techniques

The search for the soul within an individual begins with the purification of the soul. 'Tazkiyah al-nafs' is a process of purifying the soul. This process involves cleansing the soul from sins and disobedience, thereby drawing closer to God [17]. The purification of the soul occurs through two

more processes, namely ‘takhalli’ and ‘tahalli’. The process of ‘takhalli’ refers to the effort to resist one's desires by distancing oneself from committing sins [17]. This process is also known as the method of ‘mujahadah al-nafs’, which involves removing negative traits such as arrogance and envy [17].

Furthermore, ‘tahalli’ refers to the process of beautifying the soul and the individual's character [17]. In this case study, the researcher uses the approach of motivating the subject by applying virtuous traits within them. The researcher reminds the subject to always practice gratitude and patience in life. Through the application of these virtuous traits, the subject’s level of anxiety can be reduced, and it trains their soul to remain confident in Allah SWT's promises, with success for those who are patient. As stated in Surah an-Nahl:96, "We will reward those who are patient."

The following are two techniques according to Al-Ghazali, as mentioned in the book by Salasiah Hanin (2016), which the researcher has chosen to apply in the intervention appropriate for the subject of the study [14]. Table 7 below presents the selected intervention that is deemed suitable for implementation by the subject of the study.

Table 7

Intervention My Daily Study Planner.

(Source: Adapted from Quranic Soul Intervention by Ismail, M. B. 2016).

HARI	SUBJEK	SOLAT & DOA	WAKTU SOLAT	TANDATANGAN
RABU	BM	/	Zohor	-
KHAMIS	BI	/	Zohor	-
JUMAAT	GEO	/	Subuh	-
SABTU	GEO	/	Subuh	-
AHAD	BM	/	Zohor	-
ISNIN	MT	/	Asar	-
SELASA	MT	/	Asar	-
RABU	SN	/	Maghrib	-

Daily Prayers

1. "O my Lord, expand for me my chest, and ease for me my task, and untie the knot from my tongue that they may understand my speech."
2. "O Allah, forgive my sins and the sins of my parents, and have mercy on them as they have had mercy on me since childhood."
3. "O Allah, open for me the doors of knowledge and wisdom, and bestow upon me Your treasure of mercy, O Lord, the Most Generous, the Most Merciful."

The researcher adapted the previous intervention by retaining and adding several elements according to the chosen techniques. Among the elements retained:

1. The researcher retained the approach of using the Quran and Hadith by including a section of Selected Prayers under the intervention schedule so that the subject can practice it.
2. The researcher maintained the spiritual aspect of the subject by including a section of Prayer and Duas in the schedule. This is to nurture the subject’s soul to always maintain a connection and reliance on Allah in daily life.

Therapy through Prayer, as outlined by al-Ghazali in the method of applying worship, helps train the subject’s soul to always place hope in Allah SWT. Through the words of Allah SWT in Surah al-Baqarah, verse 153: "O you who have believed, seek help through patience and prayer."

Additionally, the therapy of Dua, also stated in al-Ghazali's method of applying worship, aids in bringing peace to the soul of the subject. By making dua, the heart becomes calm, and anxiety is reduced. Allah SWT says in Surah Ghafir, verse 60: "And your Lord says, 'Call upon Me; I will respond to you.'" Al-Ghazali states that prayer can bring tranquility to a restless soul.

The added element in this intervention is:

1. The researcher instructed the subject to write down the subjects studied with a friend during the eight days as preparation for the final academic exam.
2. This element is deemed appropriate to help the subject manage their anxiety regarding academic performance more effectively.

4. Conclusion

The findings of this study reveal that there are four sources of anxiety experienced by the subject of the study: the family's low-income status, being the eldest child and seen as the family's hope, weakness in certain subjects, and a lack of confidence in their potential. Based on the findings, the Al-Ghazali model appears to be effective in helping the subject manage anxiety and preventing it from worsening in the future. The effectiveness of the model can be seen through an unstructured interview with the subject after the intervention was carried out. In conclusion, the Al-Ghazali model is effective in helping to manage academic performance anxiety in Form 3 students. This study is seen as effective in addressing the issues faced by the subject. However, it may have limitations when applied to other subjects, as it depends on the level of anxiety and the causes each individual faces. The researcher offers several suggestions for further research. First, class teachers should regularly discuss students' academic performance with their parents. For example, teachers could suggest offering free remedial classes for students who are financially unable to afford them. Second, teachers should investigate the reasons for students' absenteeism and find the best solutions. Third, schools should continue the 'young teacher' program among students to help those who are struggling. Finally, the researcher suggests diversifying the types of instruments and data collection methods to ensure that the research results are more consistent and accurate. The intervention in this study applied a counseling approach introduced by Al-Ghazali. Among the implications are that it helps form students who are resilient and always place their trust in Allah SWT. Second, the Al-Ghazali model can also raise awareness among parents that every child has the potential for a bright future if they strive to change. Third, this model also reminds teachers that every student has unique strengths and potential that need to be nurtured.

Acknowledgement

This research is not funded by any grants.

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